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Formation and characterization of ZnO nano- mazes

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Introduction: Chemical synthesise of inorganic materials with hierarchical morphologies has drawn much attention due to their fundamental importance and potential applications in various fields (1). ZnO, a colorless, industrially important and multifunctional n- type semiconductor (band gap of 3.2 eV) has been widely used as gas sensor, solar cell and photocatalyst. Several methods such as thermal decomposition, spray pyrolysis, sol-gel and chemical bath deposition have been adopted to synthesize ZnO. However, these methods employ expensive reactants, complex procedures, critical experimental conditions and sophisticated equipments and make them unsuitable for large scale production.

Methods: In this paper, we have demonstrated a rapid, facile and template-free microwave assisted chemical precipitation method for the synthesis of ZnO nanomazes using Zincsulphate and sodium hydroxide. The formed mazes were characterized by XRD, SEM, SEM-EDX, TEM, FT-IR, UV-DRS, and RT- photoluminescence spectra.

Results &Discussions: The sharp diffraction peaks of ZnO matched with ZnO hexagonal wurtzite structure (JCPDS Card no: 36-1451). The average crystallite size was estimated by using Debye Scherer's formula. The surface morphology of the sample exhibit mazes-like 3D hierarchical structures. The direct band gap energy was calculated from the point of intersection made by tangent to the linear part on the abscissa of the plot of absorbance Vs wavelength by using the equation, $E = \frac{1240}{\lambda}$. PL spectrum is examined with Xenon light as the excitation source at the excitation wavelength of 325 nm in the range of 350 nm – 600 nm. The strong UV or near band edge emission peak appear at 383.98 nm and can be attributed to recombination of excitons (2). The possible mechanism for the formation of ZnO nanomaze- like morphology was explained on the basis of nucleation, growth, agglomeration and self-assembly of ZnO nanoparticles.

Conclusions: The results of the study confirmed that the synthesized ZnO mazes have wurtzite structure. The presence of surface defects and NBE emission are observed from the RT photoluminescence spectra. The presence of sulphate ions on the surface of the pre-calcinated samples influenced the growth and self-assembly of nanowalls to nanomazes.

Keywords: Walls, Mazes, Luminescence, Sulphate

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